

Synthesis and antifungal activity studies of some pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives

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Thirty four compounds of pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives namely N^1 -isonicotinoyl/ N^1 -salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one have been synthesized by the condensation of substituted phenylazo-1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-pyrimidinetrione with isonicotinic acid hydrazide/salicylic acid hydrazide. The structure of the synthesized compounds was supported by elemental analysis, mass, IR and NMR spectral data. The synthesized compounds have been also screened for their fungi toxic activity against building fungi.

The pyrazole derivatives and related compounds are well known for their broad spectrum biocidal activities and a few have fungicidal as well as pesticidal activities also^{1,2}. In this communication we have reported synthesis of thirty four pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives namely, N^1 -isonicotinoyl/ N^1 -salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one by the condensation of substituted phenylazo-1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-pyrimidinetrione with isonicotinic acid hydrazide/salicylic acid hydrazide in glacial acetic acid/DMF as condensing agent (Scheme 1). Resulting pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives have been evaluated for fungi toxic activity against building fungi and the results are reported in this communication.

Results and discussion

The individual substituted phenylazo-1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-pyrimidine on reaction with equimolar amount of nicotinic acid hydrazide/salicylic acid hydrazide in presence of glacial acetic acid/DMF resulted in the formation of the corresponding N^1 -isonicotinoyl/ N^1 -salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one. All the products (**1a-q** and **2a-q**) are crystalline stable solids and have been characterized by elemental analysis, mass, IR and ¹H NMR signals. The IR spectra of parent compound show peak at 690–825 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl) and a sharp peak at 1423 cm⁻¹ as the (N–CH₃) group is present. A number of peaks were appeared at 1545, 1560, 1620, 1690 and 2992 cm⁻¹ which indicate the presence of C–N str., C=C str., (C=N pyridine) C=O str. and (H bonded OH), respectively. Characterizations of -N=N- stretching vibration in aromatic azo compounds is difficult because of the interference of the -C=C- ring vibrations, however

Lafewre *et al.*³ have been reported that the consistent appearance of -N=N- stretching vibration in the region of 1585–1569 cm⁻¹ for azo functionality in aromatic azo compound and in case of synthesized compound characteristics band was recorded at 1580 cm⁻¹. A characteristic peak at 1700 cm⁻¹ appeared due to presence of bicyclic ring and a peak at 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O) of tertiary amide having nitrogen in diazole ring was recorded, which helped in establishing the structure of synthesized compounds.

Bioactivity : Compounds **1a-q** and **2a-q** were individually screened for their fungi toxic activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium frequentans* by adopting food poisoning technique. The results in term of radial growth in mm along with the statistical analysis of the data have been presented in Table 1. The test samples have been tested at 100 and 500 ppm concentration and compared with the solvent control. The potato dextrose agar nutrient medium was poisoned with test compound and using three replica sets radial growth was measured to evaluate their fungi toxic activity. All the compounds except **1a**, **1m**, **1n**, **1p**, **1q**, **2a**, **2p** and **2q** were found to be significantly active against both the fungi. **2f** was found to be most effective in reducing the radial growth of the mycelium at both concentrations and in the case of both fungi, zero radial growth were observed. **2h** was also found to be most effective in reducing the radial growth of mycelium at 500 ppm and in the case of *Aspergillus niger*, zero radial growth was observed. These observations reveal that a bulky substituents (2,4,5-trichloro and 2-chloro-4-nitro) and presence of phenolic functional group in the case of N^1 -salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one (**2**) enhances the fungi toxic activity against both fungi, in con-

Table 1. Fungicidal activity of the compounds **1** and **2**

Compd.	Yield (%)	R	Average radial growth in mm			
			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		<i>Penicillium frequentans</i>	
			100 ppm	500 ppm	100 ppm	500 ppm
1a	60	H	65.28 (64.0–67.5)	61.37 (60.5–62.0)	70.28 (69.0–71.0)	58.29 (57.0–59.0)
1b	63	2-Cl	43.19 (42.5–45.0)	37.08 (36.5–38.0)	47.25 (46.5–48.0)	38.28 (37.0–39.0)
1c	60	3-Cl	45.29 (43.5–46.0)	40.19 (39.0–41.0)	46.19 (45.0–47.0)	38.15 (37.0–39.0)
1d	65	4-Cl	44.08 (43.0–45.0)	38.02 (37.0–39.0)	46.17 (45.0–46.5)	40.00 (39.0–41.0)
1e	70	2,4-Cl ₂	38.09 (36.5–40.0)	31.31 (30.5–32.0)	37.12 (36.0–37.5)	30.78 (29.0–31.5)
1f	60	2,4,5-Cl ₃	32.25 (31.0–35.0)	22.00 (21.0–23.0)	31.05 (30.5–31.5)	21.29 (20.5–22.0)
1g	65	2,4,6-Cl ₃	40.21 (39.0–42.0)	35.04 (34.9–36.0)	40.17 (39.0–40.5)	36.08 (35.0–37.0)
1h	70	2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	35.31 (34.5–36.0)	28.25 (27.7–29.0)	36.05 (35.5–36.5)	25.08 (24.0–25.5)
1i	75	2-NO ₂	46.02 (45.0–47.0)	37.29 (36.5–38.0)	48.46 (48.0–49.0)	37.89 (36.5–39.0)
1j	62	3-NO ₂	55.28 (54.0–57.0)	37.28 (36.5–38.0)	58.88 (58.0–59.5)	38.63 (37.0–39.5)
1k	54	4-NO ₂	48.09 (47.0–49.0)	35.07 (34.0–36.0)	47.61 (46.5–48.0)	36.44 (35.0–37.0)
1l	55	3-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	42.37 (41.0–45.0)	37.39 (36.0–38.0)	40.31 (39.0–41.0)	36.08 (35.0–37.5)
1m	62	2-CH ₃	63.19 (61.5–64.0)	50.00 (49.0–51.0)	65.28 (64.0–66.0)	52.08 (51.0–52.5)
1n	73	4-CH ₃	65.22 (53.5–67.0)	51.18 (50.0–52.5)	68.76 (67.0–69.5)	52.29 (51.0–53.0)
1o	65	3-CH ₃ , 4-CH ₃	50.81 (48.5–51.5)	38.04 (37.7–39.0)	48.48 (47.5–49.5)	40.39 (39.0–41.0)
1p	70	2-OCH ₃	59.02 (58.0–60.0)	52.82 (51.0–53.0)	57.44 (56.0–58.5)	51.54 (50.0–52.0)
1q	70	4-OCH ₃	62.28 (61.0–63.0)	52.15 (51.0–53.0)	64.39 (63.0–65.0)	51.54 (50.0–52.0)
2a	67	H	60.64 (60.0–61.5)	50.39 (49.0–51.5)	65.49 (64.0–66.5)	54.43 (53.0–55.0)
2b	65	2-Cl	35.48 (34.0–36.0)	20.28 (19.0–21.5)	38.28 (37.0–39.0)	21.81 (20.5–22.0)
2c	60	3-Cl	37.84 (36.0–38.0)	20.21 (18.5–21.0)	39.19 (38.0–40.0)	24.56 (23.0–25.0)
2d	65	4-Cl	36.28 (35.0–37.0)	22.48 (21.0–23.0)	38.76 (37.5–39.5)	26.39 (25.0–27.0)
2e	68	2,4-Cl ₂	20.28 (19.0–21.0)	5.76 (5.0–6.5)	22.49 (21.0–23.0)	7.88 (6.5–8.5)
2f	60	2,4,5-Cl ₃	15.39 (14.0–16.0)	0.00 (nil)	16.48 (15.5–17.0)	0.00 (nil)
2g	65	2,4,6-Cl ₃	24.69 (23.0–26.0)	10.43 (9.0–11.0)	26.29 (25.5–27.5)	11.04 (11.0–12.0)
2h	72	2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	18.76 (17.5–19.5)	0.00 (nil)	20.49 (19.5–21.5)	8.56 (11.0–13.0)
2i	65	2-NO ₂	27.28 (26.5–28.0)	12.83 (11.0–13.5)	29.48 (28.0–30.5)	13.76 (12.0–14.5)
2j	72	3-NO ₂	33.77 (32.5–35.0)	19.41 (18.5–20.0)	35.78 (34.0–36.5)	21.14 (20.5–22.5)
2k	65	4-NO ₂	29.83 (28.0–31.0)	14.48 (14.0–15.5)	31.83 (30.0–32.0)	16.32 (15.5–17.0)
2l	59	3-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	31.49 (30.0–33.0)	18.92 (17.5–19.5)	33.33 (32.5–34.5)	20.18 (20.0–21.0)
2m	65	2-CH ₃	40.71 (39.0–42.0)	24.38 (23.0–25.0)	42.48 (41.0–43.5)	26.38 (25.0–26.5)
2n	68	4-CH ₃	44.37 (43.0–45.0)	25.78 (24.0–26.0)	46.28 (45.0–47.0)	28.03 (27.5–28.5)
2o	65	3-CH ₃ , 4-CH ₃	48.44 (47.5–50.0)	29.49 (28.0–30.0)	42.21 (48.0–50.0)	29.88 (28.5–30.0)
2p	70	2-OCH ₃	58.81 (57.5–59.5)	42.39 (41.0–43.0)	50.01 (59.0–61.5)	44.31 (43.0–44.0)
2q	62	4-OCH ₃	58.89 (57.5–70.0)	44.31 (43.0–45.0)	60.91 (69.0–72.0)	48.15 (47.5–49.0)
Control with solvent			80.00 (78.0–81.0)	80.00 (78.0–81.0)	83.19 (82.0–85.5)	83.19 (82.0–85.5)
Control			82.40 (80.0–84.5)	82.40 (80.0–84.5)	86.00 (85.0–87.0)	86.00 (85.0–87.0)
Gen. mean			45.04	33.57	46.19	34.99
S. Em.±			2.78	2.21	2.68	3.12
C.D. 5%			8.86	6.69	8.15	9.48
C.V. %			6.92	7.43	6.85	10.31

formity with the earlier results reported in literature⁴. Also, *N*¹-salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one (**2**) have been found to show stronger fungicidal activity than *N*¹-isonicotinoyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one (**1**).

R =

1, 2a H	1, 2j 3-NO ₂
1, 2b 2-Cl	1, 2k 4-NO ₂
1, 2c 3-Cl	1, 2l 3-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃
1, 2d 4-Cl	1, 2m 2-CH ₃
1, 2e 2,4-Cl ₂	1, 2n 4-CH ₃
1, 2f 2,4,5-Cl ₃	1, 2o 3-CH ₃ , 4-CH ₃
1, 2g 2,4,6-Cl ₃	1, 2p 2-OCH ₃
1, 2h 2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	1, 2q 4-OCH ₃
1, 2i 2-NO ₂	

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the commercial reagents and solvents were dried and distilled by common methods before use. M.ps. was determined by open capillary method and is uncorrected. The

homogeneity and purity of the compounds were checked over thin layer chromatoplates with silica gel G (thickness 0.5 mm), developing solvent acetone/DMF (3 : 1) non-saturated chamber at room temperature. Elemental (CHN) analysis was carried out on Heraeus CHN-rapid analyzer. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker WM-400 spectrophotometer (¹H NMR at 300.13 MHz) in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as internal standard.

*N*¹-Isonicotinoyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole 4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one (**1**) :

General procedure : The individual substituted phenylazo-1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-pyrimidinetrione (0.05 mol) and equimolar amount of nicotinic acid hydrazide was refluxed in glacial acetic acid/DMF for 4 h, and contents were left overnight. The colored solid thus separated was filtered and dried. **1a** m.p. 235° (Found : C, 59.41; H, 4.32; N, 27.31. C₁₈H₁₅N₇O₂ requires : C, 59.83; H, 4.18; N, 27.13%); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.20 (6H, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.52–7.98 (5H, m, aromatic-H), 7.12 (dd, 2,4-pyridinecarbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1b** 212°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.18 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.41–7.72 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1c** 231°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.20 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.47–7.75 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.07 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.11 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1d** 205°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.24 (6H, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.20 (4H, d, aromatic-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.12 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.05 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1e** 215°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.23 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.3–7.6 (3H, m, aromatic-H), 7.11 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1f** 220°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.23 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.3–7.5 (2H, m, aromatic-H), 7.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1g** 274°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.23 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.3–7.5 (3H, m, aromatic-H), 7.09 (dd, 2,4-pyridinecarbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.07 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1h** 275°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.20 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.15–7.21 (3H, m, aromatic-H), 7.17 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz), 8.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, *J*₁ 9 Hz, *J*₂ 2 Hz). **1i** 246°, ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.24 (6H, s, 2 × N-CH₃), 7.64–

7.79 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.11 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.14 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1j** 225°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.22 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.52–7.68 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1k** 222°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.27 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.57–7.81 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1l** 233°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.27 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.3–7.5 (3H, m, aromatic-H), 7.12 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.12 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1m** 215°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.30 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.3–7.7 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.17 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.13 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1n** 240°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.32 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.5–7.9 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.12 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1o** 265°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.43 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.5–7.9 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.14 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1p** 15°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 3.55 (3H, s, aromatic-OCH₃), 7.5–7.9 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.10 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.14 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz). **1q** 245°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 3.68 (3H, s, aromatic-OCH₃), 7.5–7.9 (4H, m, aromatic-H), 7.15 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl, *ortho*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz), 8.14 (dd, 2,4-pyridine carbonyl *meta*- to C=O, J_1 9 Hz, J_2 2 Hz).

*N*¹-Salicyloyl-4'-(substituted phenylazo)-1,2-diazole-4,6-dimethyl pyrimidine-5-one (**2**):

General procedure: The individual substituted phenylazo-1,3-dimethyl-2,4,6-pyrimidinetrione (0.05 mol) and equimolar amount of salicylic acid hydrazide was refluxed in glacial acetic acid/DMF for 4 h, and contents were left overnight. The colored solid thus separated was filtered and dried. **2a** m.p. 245° (Found: C, 63.39; H, 4.52; N, 23.22. C₁₉H₁₆N₆O₂ requires: C, 63.32; H, 4.48; N, 23.32%); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.20 (6H, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.52–7.98 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2b** 253°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.18 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.41–7.72 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s,

aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2c** 232°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.20 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.47–7.75 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.2 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2d** 254°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.24 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.2–7.8 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2e** 276°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.23 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.3–7.6 (7H, m, aromatic-H), 11.7 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2f** 234°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.23 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.3–7.5 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 12.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2g** 243°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.23 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.3–7.5 (6H, m, aromatic-H), 11.2 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2h** 280°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.20 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.15–7.21 (3H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2i** 243°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.24 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.64–7.79 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.4 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2j** 225°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.22 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.52–7.68 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.3 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2k** 239°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.27 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 7.57–7.81 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.5 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2l** 265°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.27 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.5–8.1 (7H, m, aromatic-H), 11.3 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2m** 215°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.30 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.3–7.7 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 12.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2n** 282°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.32 (3H, s, aromatic-CH₃), 7.5–7.9 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 12.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2o** 270°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 2.45 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 7.5–7.9 (7H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2p** 265°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 3.68 (3H, s, aromatic-OCH₃), 7.5–7.9 (8H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange). **2q** 245°, ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 3.25 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$), 3.68 (3H, s, aromatic-OCH₃), 7.5–7.9 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 11.1 (1H, s, aromatic-OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange).

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